

TRANSLATING CULTURAL SPECIFIC TERMS

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This article discusses about some techniques in translating cultural specific terms that are unique. To translate cultural words in a text, we will observe the three ideology in translating cultural words; domesticating ideology, foreignizing ideology, and neutralizing ideology. Every translation product is unique, and translators may choose what ideology they adapt to translate the text. Are they loyal to the source text, so they want to introduce the cultural words in the target text? Do they have intention to get the target readers' understanding by looking for the equivalence meaning of the cultural specific terms in the target language?

Cultural Words: Newmark characterizes societies as the way of life and its appearances that are unconventional to a community that employments a specific dialect as its implies of expression. More particularly, he recognizes “cultural” from “universal” and “personal” dialect. The words “die, live, star, swim, reflect, and table” are universals – as a rule there's no interpretation issue there. Be that as it may, the words “monsoon, steppe, dacha, tagliatelle” are social words - there will be a translation problem unless there's social cover between the source and the target dialect (and its readership). The widespread words such as “breakfast, grasp, pile” frequently cover the all inclusive work, but not the social depiction of the referent.

Newmark clarifies that there's a interpretation issue due to the social “gap” or “distance” between the source and target dialects. Most “cultural” words are simple to identify, since they are related with a specific dialect and cannot be actually deciphered, but numerous social traditions are portrayed in conventional

dialect (“topping out a building, time, men of their word, if it's not too much trouble, mud in your eye”), where strict interpretation would misshape the meaning and an interpretation may incorporate a suitable descriptive-functional proportionate. Social objects may be alluded to by a generally culture-free nonexclusive term or classifier (e.g. “tea”) additionally the various increases in numerous societies, and you have got to account for these increases “cram, lemon, drain, rolls, cake”, different times of day) which may show up within the course of the SL content.

Culture is the item of collaboration human minds, and thus a science of culture will be a science of the foremost complex phenomenon on Soil. It'll too be a science that must be built on intrigue establishments counting hereditary qualities, neuroscience, person improvement, environment and developmental science, brain research and human studies.

According to Snell-Hornby, addressing the potential problems existing in translation between English and German, there could be five basic groups of prototypes which can be briefly brought about as what follows:

- 1) Terminology/ nomenclature
- 2) Internationally known items and sets
- 3) Concrete objects, basic level items
- 4) Word, expressing perception and evaluation often linked to socio-cultural norms
- 5) Culture-bound elements

Additionally, Newmark is on the conviction that a expansive number of words can be duplicated to assign a uncommon dialect or wording of a discourse community when that community concretes on a specific subject. In line with this hypothesis of social word, five distinctive classes of “cultural categories” are assigned from each other. Newmark states, social words can be categorized into five sorts. Those categories are as following:

1) Ecology

It is a geographical feature that can be normally distinguished from other cultural terms in that they are usually value-free, politically and commercially. It includes flora, fauna, mountain, river, natural conditions. For examples: Flora, fauna, winds, plains, hills: “honeysuckle”, “downs”, “pampas”, “plateau”, selva (Tropical rain forest), “savanna”, “paddy field”.

2) Material culture

It is the culture specific element that includes clothing, food, transportation, tools and equipments, etc. For examples: kebaya, pempek, getek, etc.

- a. Food: “zabaglione”, “sake”, “kaiserschmarren”, “Sumalak”
- b. Clothes: “anorak”, kanga (Africa), dhoti (India), Atlas (Uzbekistan).
- c. Houses and towns: kampong, bourg, bourgade, chalet, low-rise, tower
- d. Transport: bike, rickshaw, moulton, cabriolet, tilbury, caliche

3) Social culture

Work and leisure such as the names of music, games or dance that is typical in certain areas such as keroncong, kuda lumping, malam takbiran, maqom, kopi darat, Ajaki amah, condottiere, biwa, sithar, raga, reggae, rock.

4) Organizations, customs, activities, procedures, concepts

The linguistic manifestations of this concept cannot be translated into a language where the audience is unfamiliar with it, for examples; kepala desa, kelin salom, challari, sumpah pemuda, and so on.

5) Gestures and habits

In this case, there is a distinction between description and function which can be made where necessary in ambiguous cases; thus, if people smile a little when someone dies or give a thumbs-up to signal OK, put a hand on a heart while greeting someone, all of which occur in some cultures and not in others. These are activities or actions carried out from generation to generation, such as; kerja bakti, qiz oshi, kelin salom, kuyov navkar, bersila, nujuh bulan, aben, lamaran, etc.

Newmark states that many common contemplations administering the interpretation of all social words. To begin with, the extreme thought ought to be

recognition of the social accomplishments alluded to within the SL content, and regard for all outside nations and their societies. Two Translation methods which are at inverse closes of the scale are regularly accessible; transference, which, ordinarily in scholarly writings, offers neighborhood color and climate, and in master writings empowers the readership to recognize the referent - especially a title or a concept – in other writings without trouble.

Translation regularly has been utilized to exchange composed or talked SL writings to comparable composed or talked TL writings. In common, the reason of translation is to duplicate different sorts of writings – counting devout, scholarly, logical, and philosophical writings – in another dialect and hence making them accessible to more extensive perusers. In case dialect were fair a classification for a set of common or widespread concepts, it would be simple to decipher from an SL to a TL; besides, beneath the circumstances the method of learning an L2 would be much less demanding than it really is. In this respect, Culler accepts that dialects are not classifications and the concepts of one dialect may contrast drastically from those of another, since each dialect verbalizes or organizes the world differently, and dialects don't essentially title categories; they verbalize their possess. The conclusion likely to be drawn from what Culler writes is that one of the troublesome problems of translation is the disparity among languages. The bigger the gap between the SL and the TL, the more difficult the transfer of message from the former to the latter will be.